

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation: generation of quantitative and translatable data

D3.4 In vitro transport data for at least 10 model drugs in both in vitro models (including validated bioanalytical methods and drug-specific properties determining blood to milk transfer rates)

Lead contributor	7 - KUL
Other contributors	20 – Bionotus 5 - UNIBO

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	19 Jul 2023	First draft version
V2.0	18/10/2023	Final reviewed version

Abstract

The aim of this deliverable was to report on the application of an *in vitro* model for the blood-milk barrier for at least 10 model medicines. The *in vitro* models were based on cultures of primary cells, more specifically human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) and Göttingen Minipigs mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs). The model medicines were amoxicillin, caffeine, cetirizine, levetiracetam, metformin, nevirapine, sertraline, tacrolimus, tenofovir, valproic acid, venlafaxine and zidovudine. Bidirectional transport experiments were performed, where basolateral-to-apical (BA) transport corresponds to the secretion from blood into human milk, and apical-to-basolateral (AB) transport represents the reuptake from human milk into the systemic circulation. Monolayer integrity was confirmed via measurement of transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) and sodium fluorescein transport as marker for the paracellular transport route. The *in vitro* models were able to distinguish between compounds with high versus intermediate and low permeability. For most compounds, no transport polarity was observed, suggesting that most compounds cross the blood-milk barrier passively. The permeability coefficients generated with the *in vitro* models can be implemented in Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic models, which will allow to make predictions of the plasma and human milk concentration-time profiles during lactation.

Introduction

In April 2019, ConcePTION was launched. ConcePTION is a private public partnership that aims to generate information about the use of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding: “Building an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding: validated and regulatory endorsed workflows for fast, optimized evidence generation.” Work Package 3 (WP3) of ConcePTION aims to generate a non-clinical testing platform to determine medicine transfer into human milk, and subsequent exposure of infants. While this platform relies on non-clinical methodologies (i.e. *in vivo* animal, *in vitro*, *in silico*), the predicted outcomes are of clinical relevance (e.g. concentration time profiles of medicines in maternal blood and milk).

An *in vitro* cell culture model for the blood milk barrier can be established based on the assumption that the mammary epithelium is the main barrier for medicine partitioning into the human milk. Cell culture models have been described relying on human or animal epithelial cell culture models, including both primary cells and cell lines. Although primary cells are more sensitive to handling and have a limited life span, they are the preferred *in vitro* models as they are most biorelevant for the *in vivo* physiology. Animal *in vitro* models can play a key role in the *in vitro* / *in vivo* extrapolation of human data, but have not always been successful due to species differences (e.g. differences in enzyme and transporter expression). Within the ConcePTION project, the Göttingen Minipigs has been proposed as the most representative animal model. Therefore, the Göttingen Minipigs mammary epithelial cells were selected as second *in vitro* model for the blood milk barrier.

The aim of this deliverable was to report on the application of an *in vitro* model (based on either human or Göttingen Minipigs mammary epithelial cells) for the blood-milk barrier for at least 10 model medicines.

Methods

1. Model compounds

The selection of at least ten model compounds was described in detail in D3.1 Report on scope and limitations of *in vivo* and *in vitro* non-clinical and computational models for drug milk excretion and breastfed infant exposure; Selection of a panel of at least 10 model compounds for initial evaluation of non-clinical models. In addition, caffeine was added because of its relevance and availability of clinical data. Furthermore, the consortium decided to not include biologicals at this stage.

The model medicines selected in WP4 were included, as *in vivo* data will become available within the ConcePTION project for these medicines. The selection criteria for the model compounds in WP4 were:

1. availability of human data;

2. diverse therapeutic areas;
3. diverse physicochemical properties;
4. societal impact of data generation;
5. ability to assess PK;
6. existence of networks to raise awareness for patients to participate in research and to develop ethical standards via empirical qualitative studies (i.e. patient groups);
7. patient compliance; and
8. feasibility to recruit a sufficient sample size for analysis at appropriate population levels for popPK
9. analytical feasibility.

The selection criteria for the additional model compounds in WP3 were:

1. diverse chemical structures and physicochemical properties;
2. clinical relevance in the lactating population;
3. quality and resolution of available reference data;
4. availability of popPK for breast milk exposure;
5. availability of PK data.

The model medicines selected in WP4 are shown in Table 1. The additional model medicines selected in WP3 are shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Model medicines selected in WP4

Medicine	MW	BCS Class	pKa	LogP	fu	Main Elimination Route
Amoxicillin	365.40	I	3.23 (acid) 7.43 (base)	0.87	0.85	Renal
Cetirizine	388.90	III	2.9 (acid) 8.0 (base) 2.2 (base)	1.50	0.07	Renal
Metformin	129.16	III	2.80 (base) 11.50 (acid)	-1.43	1.00	Renal
Venlafaxine	277.40	I	9.5 (base)	2.9	0.73	Hepatic (CYP2D6)

Molecular weight (MW, g/mol); biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS); acid dissociation constant (pKa); lipophilicity as Log₁₀ of the partition coefficient between octanol and water (LogP); fraction unbound in human plasma (fu).

Table 2 Model medicines selected in WP3

Medicine	MW	BCS Class	pKa	LogP	fu	Main Elimination Route
Caffeine	194.20	I	0.80 (base)	-0.07	0.70	Hepatic (CYP1A2)
Levetiracetam	170.21	I	- (neutral)	-0.60	0.90	Renal & esterase
Nevirapine	266.30	II	2.8 (base)	1.93	0.40	Hepatic (CYP3A4)
Sertraline	306.00	II	9.43 (base)	5.5	0.023	Hepatic (CYPs)

Tacrolimus	804.0	II	9.95 (acid)	2.7	0.99	Hepatic (CYP3A4)
Tenofovir	287.21	III	1.35 (acid) 6.70 (acid) 3.80 (base)	1.87	0.993	Renal
Valproic acid	144.21	I	4.80 (acid)	2.75	0.14	Hepatic (UGTs)
Zidovudine	267.24	I	9.7 (acid)	0.05	0.80	Hepatic (UGT2B7)

Molecular weight (MW, g/mol); biopharmaceutics classification system (BCS); acid dissociation constant (pKa); lipophilicity as Log₁₀ of the partition coefficient between octanol and water (LogP); fraction unbound in human plasma (fu).

2. Culture of human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs)

Ethical approval for acquiring, passaging, storing and culturing hMECs was obtained from the Ethics Committee Research (EC Research) UZ/KU Leuven (S675546).

Human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs, Thermo Fisher Scientific, A10565) expanded and characterized as previously described in deliverable 3.2 were cultured on Primaria™ tissue culture flasks (Corning, 353813 and 353824). hMECs were seeded at a density of 5×10^3 cells/cm² in serum-free mammary epithelial cell basal medium (PromoCell, C-21210) supplemented with 1% anti-anti solution (Gibco, 15240-062) and a supplementmix (PromoCell, C-39110) containing 0.004 mL/mL Bovine Pituitary Extract, 10 ng/mL Epidermal Growth Factor (recombinant human), 5 µg/mL insulin (recombinant human), and 0.5 µg/mL hydrocortisone. Medium was changed every 2-3 days.

For *in vitro* experiments, cells between the 8th and 9th passage, were seeded on 24-well polyethylene terephthalate transwell inserts (Falcon, 353095) with a pore size of 0.4 µm and cell growth area of 0.3 cm². For transwell culture, hMECs were seeded at a density of 1×10^5 cells/insert in mammary epithelial cell basal medium supplemented with 1% anti-anti solution, 10 % foetal bovine serum (Merck Chemicals Ltd, F9665-500ML), 10 ng/mL Epidermal Growth Factor (recombinant human), 5 µg/mL insulin (recombinant human), and 0.5 µg/mL hydrocortisone. Medium was changed every 2-3 days.

3. Isolation and culture of minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs)

Tissue samples were collected from animals enrolled in the experimental lactation study, within the ConcePTION project framework, approved by the Italian Ministry of Health as dictated by D.Lgs 26/2014 (approval n° 32/2021-PR).

Minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) were isolated and characterized following the isolation protocol that was previously developed [1] from three sows (n=3). Briefly, after appropriate disinfection with Betadine (10% cutaneous solution) and ethanol 70%, portions of mammary gland were isolated, collected and the cells were isolated by combining enzymatic and mechanical dissociation using the Miltenyi GentleMACS Octo Dissociator.

mpMECs were cultured on Primaria™ tissue culture flasks (Corning, 353813 and 353824). mpMECs were cultured at a density of 20×10^3 cells/cm² in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium: Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM-F12, Gibco, 31330-038) supplemented with 1% anti-anti solution (Gibco, 15240-062), 10% foetal bovine serum (Life Technologies, 10500-064), 5 ng/mL Epidermal Growth Factor (recombinant human) (PromoCell, C-39110), 5 µg/mL insulin (recombinant human) (PromoCell, C-39110), and 0.5 µg/mL hydrocortisone (PromoCell, C-39110). Medium was changed every 2-3 days.

For *in vitro* experiments, cells between the 7th and 16th passage, were seeded on 24-well polyethylene terephthalate transwell inserts (Falcon, 353095) with a pore size of 0.4 µm and cell growth area of 0.3 cm². Cells isolated from three different animals were pooled. For transwell culture, mpMECs were seeded at a density of 1.5×10^5 cells/insert in the same medium as used for culture of mpMECs. Medium was changed every 2-3 days.

4. Application of the *in vitro* models

The transport experiments were performed when a tight monolayer was obtained on the transwell inserts, based on prior confirmation by transepithelial electrical resistance and sodium fluorescein transport. The *in vitro* experiments were performed after 35 days for hMECs, and after 4 days for mpMECs. One day or 3 hours before the experiment, the medium was changed (0.3 mL apical and 0.72 mL basolateral) for hMECs and mpMECs.

Individual stock solutions of the model medicines at 100 mM in DMSO (except tenofovir 10 mM in ultrapure water and metformin 100 mM in ultrapure water) were stored at -20°C. Subsequently, dosing solutions with multiple medicines were prepared in transwell culture medium (see section 2 and 3) as follows:

- A. amoxicillin, nevirapine, valproic acid, and cetirizine;
- B. metformin, levetiracetam, tenofovir and zidovudine;
- C. venlafaxine, tacrolimus, and sertraline;
- D. caffeine.

Medium was added to the receptor compartment and the dosing solution was added to the donor compartment to obtain a final concentration of 50 µM of each medicine in medium (0.2% DMSO), and final volumes of 0.5 mL in the apical compartment and 1.2 mL in the basolateral compartment. Three to six inserts, depending on the experiment, were used for each dosing solution. Bidirectional transport experiments were performed for 2 hours, at 37 °C under gentle shaking (120 rpm). A sample was taken from each dosing solution. Receptor compartment samples (half of the compartment volume) were taken at 30, 60 and 90 min, and medium was added to replace the sample volume. The dilutions were taken into account when calculating the cumulative amount transported. At the end of the experiment (120 min), samples were taken from the receptor and donor compartments. Three independent experiments (with newly seeded cells) were performed to confirm the results. The apparent permeability coefficient was calculated using Equation 1. Samples below the limit of quantification were not used when calculating the slope of the cumulative amount transported curve.

$$Permeability_{apparent} \left(\frac{cm}{s} \right) = \frac{dQ}{dt} \left(\frac{signal}{s} \right) * \frac{1}{Area_{membrane}(cm^2) * Concentration_{donor} \left(\frac{signal}{mL} \right)} \quad (1)$$

with *signal* the area-under-the-curve of the compound peak obtained after LC-MSMS bioanalysis and corrected for the dilutions made during sample preparation and the injection volume

Transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) was measured before and after the experiment. The resistance was measured at 37°C in medium, using an Epithelial Volt/Ohm Meter 2 (EVOM2, World Precision Instruments). The TEER was calculated using Equation Equation 2:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Transepithelial electrical resistance } (\Omega * cm^2) \\ & = (Resistance_{total}(\Omega) - Resistance_{blank}(\Omega)) * Area_{membrane}(cm^2) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The integrity of the monolayer was confirmed after the experiment via measurement of sodium fluorescein transport. The medium was replaced by 0.5 mL sodium fluorescein (2.66 mM) in transport buffer apical, and 1.2 mL transport buffer basolateral. Transport buffer consisted of HBSS (Lonza), with addition of 10 mM HEPES (VWR International) and 25 mM glucose (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Sodium fluorescein transport was determined after 1 hour, at 37°C under gentle shaking (120 rpm). A sample was taken from the basolateral compartment after 1 hour. The concentration of sodium fluorescein in the samples was measured via fluorescence intensity ($\lambda = 490/524$ nm) using a Tecan Infinite M200 plate reader (Tecan Group Ltd., Männedorf, Austria). Transport buffer was used as blank, and a calibration curve was prepared with concentrations of sodium fluorescein ranging from 207.8125 nM (0.0078 %) to 3.325 µM (0.125 %). The transport of sodium fluorescein (%) was calculated using Equation 3:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Transport}_{\text{sodium fluorescein}}(\%) \\
 &= \frac{\text{Concentration}_{\text{sample}} (\mu\text{M})}{\text{Concentration}_{\text{donor}} (\mu\text{M})} * \frac{\text{Volume}_{\text{basolateral}} (\text{mL})}{\text{Volume}_{\text{apical}} (\text{mL})} * 100 \% \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

5. Bioanalysis

Standard solutions of test compounds at 50 μM , 500 nM and 5 nM were prepared by spiking stock solutions (5 mM in DMSO) of model compounds and serial dilution with transwell culture medium (see section 2 and 3). These standard samples were processed along with study samples and used for qualification of analytical runs.

The determination of model compounds in samples generated from *in vitro* experiments was based on LC-MS/MS analysis using Shimadzu LCMS-8050 system (Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source. During study sample analysis, four analytical methods and sample preparation workflows were developed and verified for separate analyses of four mixtures of model compounds.

A. Method for amoxicillin, nevirapine, valproic acid, and cetirizine

50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of 0.1% formic acid in methanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Kinetex® C8 (100 x 2.1 mm, 2.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of gradient mixture of a) 10 mM ammonium acetate and b) methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 6.5 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV, except for valproic acid at negative mode with ionizing voltage of 3 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out for amoxicillin, nevirapine and cetirizine using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. Selected ion monitoring (SIM) was used for determining valproic acid. MRM transition or SIM target ion, and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

B. Method for metformin, levetiracetam, tenofovir and zidovudine

50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of acetonitrile. The mixture was centrifuged at 16260 g for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Luna Omega® Polar C18 (50 x 2.1 mm, 1.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of gradient mixture of a) 0.1% formic acid in water and b) 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 6.5 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. MRM transition and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

C. Method for venlafaxine, tacrolimus, and sertraline

50 μL of study sample was mixed with 200 μL of methanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 μL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 μL (for donor samples) or 10 μL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Luna Omega® Polar C18 (50 x 2.1 mm, 1.6 μm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase

consisted of gradient mixture of a) 10 mM ammonium acetate and b) 0.1% formic acid in methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 5 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. MRM transition and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

D. Method for caffeine

50 µL of study sample was mixed with 200 µL of methanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 10 min at 21°C. Then, 100 µL of the supernatant was mixed with 100 µL of water in a 96-well plate. 1 µL (for donor samples) or 10 µL (for receiver samples) was injected for analysis.

Chromatographic separation was carried out on an Phenomenex Kinetex® C8 (100 x 2.1 mm, 2.6µm) column at 40°C. The autosampler temperature was set at 15°C. The mobile phase consisted of gradient mixture of a) 0.1% formic acid in water and b) methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the run time was 2 min. MS detection was performed at positive mode using ionizing voltage of 4 kV. The interface temperature was set at 300°C and desolvation line temperature at 250°C, with ultrahigh-purity nitrogen for the drying gas (10 L/min), nebulizer gas (3 L/min) and heating gas (10 L/min). Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was carried out using argon as collision gas (CID), with a dwell time of 50 msec for each transition. MRM transition and CID for each analyte are shown in Table 3.

LC-MS conditions were optimized to achieve good sensitivity and chromatographic separation of analytes. The lower limits of quantification of methods are indicated in Table . Chromatograms of compounds involved in *in vitro* experiments are shown in Figure 1-4.

Table 3. MRM transitions or SIM target ions used in LC-MS/MS analysis.

	Analyte	MRM* Transitions or SIM* target (m/z)	CE*	Lower Limit of quantification (as % of 50 µM)
Method A	Amoxicillin	366.1 -> 114.2	-20	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Nevirapine	267.2 -> 225.95	-24	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Valproic acid	143.1 (SIM)	9	1 µM (2.00 %)
	Cetirizine	389.2 -> 201.15	-39	5 nM (0.01 %)
Method B	Metformin	130.2 -> 60.2	-14	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Tenofovir	288.1 -> 176.1	-24	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Levetiracetam	171.2 -> 125.9	-15	20 nM (0.04 %)
	Zidovudine	268.2 -> 127.05	-11	5 nM (0.01 %)
Method C	Venlafaxine	278.3 -> 57.9	-17	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Tacrolimus	821.4 -> 768.3	-26	5 nM (0.01 %)
	Sertraline	306.0 -> 158.85	-18	5 nM (0.01 %)
Method D	Caffeine	198.09 -> 138.2	-19	5 nM (0.01 %)

* MRM: Multiple Reaction Monitoring; SIM: Selected Ion Monitoring; CE: Collision Energy.

Figure 1. Chromatograms of cetrizine, nevirapine, amoxicillin and valproic acid at sample level of 50 μ M obtained with method A, from top to bottom respectively.

Figure 2. Chromatograms of tenofovir, levetiracetam, zidovudine and metformin at sample level of 50 μ M obtained with method B, from top to bottom respectively.

Figure 3. Chromatograms of sertraline, venlafaxine and tacrolimus at sample level of $10 \mu\text{M}$ obtained with method C, from top to bottom respectively.

Figure 4. Chromatograms of caffeine at sample level of $1 \mu\text{M}$ obtained with method D.

Results

1. Application of the *in vitro* models

The transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) before the experiments is shown in Figure 5. The TEER after the experiments is shown in Figure 6. Finally, the TEER after the experiments is shown as percentage of the

TEER before the experiments in Figure 7. The sodium fluorescein transport (%) is shown in Figure 8. The bidirectional transport results for the model medicines are shown in Figure 9 for hMECs and in Figure 10 for mpMECs. Basolateral-to-apical (BA) transport corresponds to the secretion from blood into human milk, whereas apical-to-basolateral (AB) transport represent the reuptake from human milk into the systemic circulation.

Figure 5 Trans epithelial electrical resistance before the actual transport experiments.

A boxplot is shown for trans epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) before each experiment. The line in the boxplot corresponds to the median, and the lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles). Individual points represent 'outliers'. The experiments with human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) are shown in red, whereas the experiment with minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) are shown in blue.

Figure 6 Trans epithelial electrical resistance after the actual transport experiments
 A boxplot is shown for trans epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) after each experiment. The line in the boxplot corresponds to the median, and the lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles). Individual points represent 'outliers' data. The experiments with human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) are shown in red, whereas the experiment with minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) are shown in blue.

Figure 7 Transepithelial electrical resistance after the actual transport relatively to the initial value before the experiments. A boxplot is shown for transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) after each experiment as percentage of the initial TEER value before the experiments. The line in the boxplot corresponds to the median, and the lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles). Individual points represent 'outliers' data. The experiments with human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) are shown in red, whereas the experiment with minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) are shown in blue.

Figure 8 Sodium fluorescein transport (%)

A boxplot is shown for sodium fluorescein transport (%) after each experiment. The line in the boxplot corresponds to the median, and the lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles). Individual points represent 'outliers' data. The experiments with human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) are shown in red, whereas the experiment with minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) are shown in blue.

Figure 9 In vitro transport data in human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) Apparent permeability (P_{app} , $E-06$ cm/s) of the selected model medicines in human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs). Basolateral-to-apical (BA) transport corresponds to the secretion from blood into human milk, whereas apical-to-basolateral (AB) transport represent the reuptake from human milk into the systemic circulation. Points represent the mean P_{app} values for each experiment ($n=6$, except for L-021 $n=3$), with each independent experiment represented by a different color.

Figure 10 In vitro transport data in minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) Apparent permeability (P_{app} , $E-06$ cm/s) of the selected model medicines in minipig mammary epithelial cells (hMECs). Basolateral-to-apical (BA) transport corresponds to the secretion from blood into human milk, whereas apical-to-basolateral (AB) transport represent the reuptake from milk into the systemic circulation. Points represent the mean P_{app} values for each experiment ($n=6$), with each independent experiment represented by a different color.

Discussion

The aim of this deliverable was to report on the application an *in vitro* model (based on either human or Göttingen Minipig mammary epithelial cells) for the blood-milk barrier for at least ten model medicines. The medicines were selected based on the availability of clinical data, as well as diversity in physicochemical

properties. The selected model medicines were amoxicillin, caffeine, cetirizine, levetiracetam, metformin, nevirapine, sertraline, tacrolimus, tenofovir, valproic acid, venlafaxine and zidovudine.

The selected *in vitro* models were human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) and Göttingen Minipigs mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs). Both are primary cells, and are therefore the most biorelevant option, although they are quite sensitive to handling and have a limited life span. mpMECs were selected as the Göttingen Minipigs is the animal model that corresponds best to the human situation for lactation. One remarkable advantage of the mpMECs *in vitro* model is that the cells require a much shorter maturation time on the transwell inserts (4 days, compared to 35 days for hMECs).

The monolayer integrity was checked via measurement of TEER before and after the experiment, and transport of sodium fluorescein through the barrier after the experiments. Based on these results, it is clear that hMECs form a much tighter barrier compared to mpMECs. This is shown by higher TEER values, and lower sodium fluorescein transport. Variability on the relative TEER is similar for hMECs and mpMECs with intra-experiment coefficient of variation (CV) ranging from 15 % to 32 % for hMECs and 17% to 28 % for mpMECs and inter-experiment CV of 24 % for hMECs and 17 % for mpMECs. Importantly, both *in vitro* models are able to distinguish between paracellular and transcellular transport, as shown previously using atenolol and propranolol as probe substrates (unpublished data). The experiments performed show proof of concept for the ability to rank compounds, even at very low TEER values observed in mpMECs *in vitro* model. Nevertheless, it is recommended to measure TEER and sodium fluorescein transport in future experiments to further investigate the correlation with the apparent permeability. Furthermore, it is recommended to exclude inserts with a TEER value below 35 from the experiments, as it was observed that these lead to significantly higher apparent permeability.

The *in vitro* models were both able to distinguish between compounds with low (e.g. amoxicillin) and high (e.g. caffeine) permeability. Overall, the permeability coefficients were higher in the mpMEC *in vitro* model compared to the hMEC *in vitro* model. This is in line with the higher resistance of the hMECs to electrical current. Integration of the *in vitro* data in both *in vitro* models, together with the *in vivo* studies that are currently ongoing in ConcePTION WP3 for Göttingen Minipig and WP4 for humans will should allow for exploring *in vitro* / *in vivo* extrapolation algorithms for passage across the blood/milk barrier.

In terms of data obtained from independent experiments, inter-experiment variability in transepithelial transport remained rather limited (CV of 28 % for hMECs and 25 % for mpMECs), especially considering the sometimes pronounced differences in TEER values. Nevertheless, it seems recommended that calibration of transport data between different experiments is pursued, for instance by using reference compounds to be repeated in every experiment aimed at determining permeability coefficients for novel compounds. Such an approach is typically used for transepithelial transport experiments, for instance across Caco-2 monolayers [2].

For the majority of the medicines selected, there was no clear polarity in transport across the blood-milk barrier, i.e; transport rates were comparable in both directions. This suggests that there was minimal impact of (saturated) active transport via membrane transporters known to mediate cellular uptake and efflux of xenobiotics, including medicines. For the medicines without clear polarity in transport, the permeability across the blood milk barrier is mainly driven by passive mechanisms, and can be predicted based on physicochemical properties (e.g. lipophilicity, pKa values, molecular weight and protein binding). The highest polarity in transport was observed for sertraline. Sertraline has been described as a high affinity substrate for P-glycoprotein (P-gp) [3]. However, P-gp is not expected to play an important role at the blood milk barrier, which was also confirmed previously in the *in vitro* models using fexofenadine as probe substrate (unpublished data). The main transporter at the blood-milk barrier is breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP). BCRP-expressing Madin-Darby canine kidney (MDCK) II cell monolayers have for example been used to study the BCRP-related secretion of medicines into the human milk [4]. The selected set of model medicines does not include any medicines with important BCRP affinity.

The permeability values derived from both *in vitro* models can be used as input for physiologically-based pharmacokinetic models (PBPK models). These are bottom-up *in silico* models. PBPK models combine medicine-specific parameters with physiology-specific parameters to predict the pharmacokinetic profile of a medicine. PBPK models can be used to predict the concentration-time profile of medicines in plasma and human milk of a lactating population. The clearance between plasma and human milk can be calculated by

multiplying the permeability values derived from the *in vitro* model with the surface area of the blood-milk barrier.

Conclusion

Human mammary epithelial cells (hMECs) and Göttingen Minipig mammary epithelial cells (mpMECs) were used to measure the *in vitro* transport data across the blood-milk barrier for at least 10 model medicines. Both models were able to distinguish between high, intermediate and low permeability compounds, although the hMECs form a tighter barrier. The permeability coefficients generated with these *in vitro* models will be used as input for PBPK models, which will allow to predict the pharmacokinetic profile of the medicines in plasma and human milk.

Furthermore, the possible correlation between permeability coefficients of model compounds and the corresponding *in vivo* milk/plasma ratios in humans and Göttingen Minipigs will be explored. In addition, possible correlation between the permeability coefficients obtained in this study and those reported across Caco-2 monolayers will be evaluated.

References

1. Bernardini C, La Mantia D, Salaroli R, Zannoni A, Nauwelaerts N, Deferm N, Ventrella D, Bacci ML, Sarli G, Bouisset-Leonard M, Annaert P, Forni M. Development of a Pig Mammary Epithelial Cell Culture Model as a Non-Clinical Tool for Studying Epithelial Barrier-A Contribution from the IMI-ConcePTION Project. *Animals (Basel)*. 2021 Jul 5;11(7):2012. doi: 10.3390/ani11072012. PMID: 34359140; PMCID: PMC8300391.
2. Certara. SimCYP workshop: 3. Gut Wall Passive Permeability (2022).
3. Burgess G, Hoogkamer H, Collings L, Dingemans J. Mutual pharmacokinetic interactions between steady-state bosentan and sildenafil. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*. 2008 Jan;64(1):43-50. doi: 10.1007/s00228-007-0408-z. Epub 2007 Nov 27. PMID: 18040672.
4. Ito N, Ito K, Ikebuchi Y, Toyoda Y, Takada T, Hisaka A, Oka A, Suzuki H. Prediction of Drug Transfer into Milk Considering Breast Cancer Resistance Protein (BCRP)-Mediated Transport. *Pharm Res*. 2015 Aug;32(8):2527-37. doi: 10.1007/s11095-015-1641-2. Epub 2015 Feb 19. PMID: 25690342.

